

FORMATION OF INTERCULTURAL AND COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF FUTURE TEACHERS**Muratkyzy N.***Master student**The Kazakh Ablai Khan University of International Relations and World Languages
Kazakhstan, Almaty***Abstract**

The article is devoted to the formation of intercultural *and communicative* competence of students of pedagogical universities. The author substantiates the identification of the stages of formation of intercultural competence, corresponding to the stages of mastering a foreign culture by M. Bennett, determines their purpose and gives methodological recommendations for organizing training at each stage. The article presents a theoretical substantiation of the formation of intercultural communicative competence among students, the components of competencies, the components of intercultural communicative competence are considered.

Keywords: intercultural and communicative competence; stages of intercultural competence forming; stages of foreign culture mastering

In modern education, a special role in the training of specialists is acquiring a focus on personality and competence, which makes it possible to significantly facilitate the process of students' adaptation to the professional environment and increase its competitiveness. At the present stage of development of society, the problem of adequate mutual understanding in the process of intercultural communication is of particular relevance in connection with new trends in social development.

The formulation of competence almost completely coincides with the definition of intercultural competence by T. G. Grushevitskaya, who considers this concept as "a positive attitude towards the presence of various ethnic and cultural groups in society and the voluntary adaptation of social and political institutions of society to the needs of different cultural groups" [1. p. 277].

In this regard, pedagogical universities should pay special attention to the problem of the formation of this competence among future teachers of foreign languages. By intercultural competence, students of a pedagogical university understand their ability to carry out intercultural professional communication, taking into account knowledge of the norms of verbal and non-verbal behavior in their own and other cultures. This approach not only reflects the structure of the phenomenon, but also determines the content of the relevant training, namely, knowledge of the linguistic and cultural orientation and their application in situations of professional communication.

The formation of intercultural competence is often associated with the study of a dedicated foreign language, although, as V.G. Roshchupkin's study shows, cross-cultural literacy of students is expected learning, this process may be required and how to acquire interdisciplinary connections between pedagogy and teaching methods, philosophy, cultural studies, psychology, since "general didactic provisions are presented indirectly in teaching a foreign language" [2. p.136].

In the context of higher education, for the successful implementation of this concept, it is necessary to single out several particular goals and a list of relevant tasks aimed at their solution. Intercultural professional and communicative competence as a general goal of language training of a graduate of a non-linguistic university has several private goals that make up its macro level [3, p. 98]:

1) improvement of intracultural competence as the readiness and ability of a non-linguist student to identify, understand and interpret concepts, ideas, norms and rules of their own professional linguistic culture;

2) the formation of foreign cultural competence as the readiness and ability of a graduate of a non-linguistic university to identify, understand and interpret the concepts, ideas, norms and rules of a different professional linguistic culture;

3) the development of intercultural competence as a willingness and ability to identify, understand, interpret, compare and discuss concepts, ideas, norms, rules that make up one's own and other linguistic society's professional worldviews.

It is assumed that students immanently master cross-cultural skills and are prepared for real communication, but practice shows that the knowledge component, even with practical training, is not enough for adequate communication with representatives of other cultures. We believe that the reason lies in the absence of a theoretically substantiated system of exercises that takes into account the phased formation of any action.

As a theoretical basis for the development of such a system, in our opinion, the stages of mastering a foreign culture by M. Bennett can be taken, which make it possible to trace the development of an individual's ideas about a foreign culture and his desire / ability to adapt to the rules of behavior within this culture [1. p. 268]. We presented the results of studying the theory of M. Bennett in the table, which also contains our recommendations for the educational process and the goal for each specific stage.

Stages of formation of intercultural competence

Stages of mastering a foreign culture by M. Bennet	Characteristics of the stage	Recommendations for the educational process
<i>Ethnocentric stages:</i> Denial Isolation Separation	Denial of cultural differences between peoples. Physical isolation (separate tribes), partial isolation is possible at the level of broad categories: Europeans and Asians. Separation - the erection of physical or social barriers on racial, religious, political grounds.	Organization of international meetings, acquaintance with foreign music, cuisine, literature. <i>Purpose:</i> to recognize the existence of inter-cultural differences.
Protection Defamation (slander) Superiority Reverse development	Perception of cultural differences as a threat to one's existence. Negative assessment, the formation of negative stereotypes up to the actions of extremist organizations. Emphasizing one's high cultural status, pride, explains the emergence of the term "developing countries / third world countries". Not an obligatory stage, often manifested in people living abroad, denigration of their native culture, recognition of the superiority of another.	Cultivating cultural self-respect in the face of differences. Pay special attention to those elements of culture that are common to all interacting cultures, and especially to what is positive in them. <i>Purpose:</i> acceptance of the presence of cultural traditions as an objective reality
Derogation Physical Universalism Transcendent Universalism	The stage of minimization is the last attempt to maintain an ethnocentric position. Differences are openly acknowledged and not judged negatively. The human essence is one (general physical characteristics). All people are the product of a single principle (man is created in the image and likeness of God).	Emphasis that the satisfaction of similar physical needs occurs in a specific social and cultural context (eg, dining at home or in a cafe). Acquaintance with empirical material that emphasizes the importance of the social context of human behavior. Stories about their own experience of contacts, meetings with representatives of another culture. <i>Purpose:</i> to show the specific features of "universal" categories, the formation of a value attitude to culture.
<i>Ethnorelativistic stages</i> Recognition Respect for differences in behavior Respect for differences in value systems	Recognition is approval. The most obvious difference is the language. Awareness that languages are different in reflecting different linguistic pictures of the world. Acceptance of different views of the world, which are the basis of cultural variations in behavior.	Introduction to non-verbal behavior. Analysis of situations demonstrating various types of behavior, analysis of the scale of values, proverbs. <i>Purpose:</i> to gain knowledge about cultural differences.
Adaptation Empathy Pluralism	Adaptation to the conditions of another culture. Culture is not a frozen fact, but a process, therefore it is better to say not that people have a culture, but that they are involved in it, so a person can temporarily behave acceptable to a foreign culture without feeling a threat to his own values. Empathy is the ability to experience different sensations in the process of communication, for example, sympathy. Full understanding of differences in specific situations, the result of personal experience of living in a foreign culture (usually at least 2 years, children of emigrants)	Analysis and reproduction of alternative communication skills and behavioral models. <i>Purpose:</i> conscious simulation of behavior depending on the cultural affiliation of the interlocutor, understanding the value system.

Integration	Complete adaptation to a foreign culture, which begins to feel like one's own. Formation of a multicultural personality.	Playing situations from the point of view of different cultures and analyzing the choice of this behavioral strategy. <i>Purpose:</i> interpretation of cultural differences, formation of the skill of switching from one behavioral model to another.
Contextual assessment	Analysis and assessment of the situation of the possibility of cultural behavior options (to act in Japanese or in Russian).	
Constructive marginality	The personality is outside the cultural framework, there is no natural cultural identity, there is no absolutely correct behavior.	

Thus, intercultural communicative competence is an important professional component of a modern specialist, the basis which are laid during training in higher educational institutions. An important task of modern higher institutions is to create favorable conditions for the formation of intercultural communicative competence of future specialists and the use of modern computer information technologies in full.

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FORMATIVE ASSESSMENT AS AN EFFECTIVE WAY OF ASSESSMENT OF STUDENTS' ACHIEVEMENTS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING PROCESS

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Abstract

Today, the traditional education system cannot meet the demands of a volatile society, which eventually becomes unstable. Although they have academic knowledge, students often cannot apply their knowledge in a changing life. In accordance with this, the modern education system needs to introduce new approaches in the system of assessing students' educational achievements, in the formation of their general educational competencies. The use of one of such new approaches in the assessment of students' academic achievements- formative assessment increases students' motivation to study, develops skills of academic independence, influences the formation of personality who will be able to compete and work in his/ her future international labor market meeting all the requirements of modern society.

Keywords: criteria-based assessment, formative assessment, students' achievement, assessment for learning, foreign language

Nowadays in connection with modern tendencies in the development of education system of the world evaluation of students' activities has become an important element of the pedagogical process, and evaluation is a powerful pedagogical tool that performs a particular task of the teacher. Any evaluation activity is based on the student's or teacher's need to get information about how effectively their interaction takes place during the educational process.

The assessment system is an effective tool not only for measuring student achievement in foreign language teaching process, but also for improving the quality of education. Therefore, the evaluation system is understood not only as the scale that is used when setting marks, but, above all, the mechanism itself for the implementation of diagnostic and developmental

activities of the teacher and student as full participants in the educational process. Assessment is also a reflection of the process of interaction between the state and the school, teacher and student, school and parents.

Assessment and teaching process are interrelated processes. There are three interdependent types of assessment: diagnostic, formative and summative. The teacher will not be able to apply formative assessment at the proper level without the results of the diagnostic assessment. And the quality of formative assessment in the lesson will affect the results of summative assessment. By maintaining this consistency in the assessment, teachers can achieve a high level of learning.

The concept of "assessment for learning" gained its fame in 1999 after the publication of a brochure with the same name, the author of which was the Assessment